

Women, Nature and Patriarchy: An Ecofeminist Analysis of Mahasweta Devi's Novel *The Book of the Hunter*

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Abstract: *Ecofeminism operates as a critical lens that interrogates the interlinked structures of environmental degradation and patriarchal control. By theorizing the mutual subjugation of nature and women, it resists intersecting hierarchies and posits an ethical paradigm of justice, care, and ecological balance. Ecofeminists also take into the consideration the suffering of women, subjugation of indigenous people and marginalized strata of life, simultaneously, depicting the ecological depletion induced by social structures such as patriarchy, colonialism and capitalism. This research paper explores the fictional narrative, *The Book of the Hunter* which delineates on tribal identity, and environmental decline. This research paper adopts the frame work of ecofeminism to map the habitational struggle of Shabar community; particularly the women; induced by gradual destruction of the locale wherein the tribe dwells. The research paper reflects on the parallel exploitation of the women of Shabar tribe, the broader socio-environmental crisis by illustrating how environmental degradation and patriarchal forces collectively undermine not only indigenous communities and the tribal women but also distort the nature with same force. It offers a critique of ecological concerns and struggles of indigenous women and further talks about the importance of environmental sustainability and preservation of tribal customs and rituals.*

Keywords: Ecofeminism, Tribal, Anthropocentrism, Androcentric, Environmental degradation.

Ecofeminism is a theoretical and activist movement that draws a relation between environmental degradation and exploitation of women. Ecofeminism propounds that both environment and women are oppressed due to patriarchy and capitalistic forces. The fundamental argument of ecofeminism is to explain that colonialism and patriarchy treat nature and women as resources to be exploited by their imperialistic methods and policies that govern the social and market structures. Ecofeminism focuses on the impact of environmental deprivation on marginalized communities particularly women in indigenous and rural societies. Ecofeminist scholars explain how in the scheme of patriarchy, both women and nature appear as the other. Trish Glazebrook in her paper, “Karen Warren's Ecofeminism” states:

Environmental and feminist issues have their basis in the logic of domination that underwrites patriarchy, so feminists and environmentalists can form an alliance in the face of a common enemy, as it were, but for the connection between feminism and ecology to be necessary, it would have to be shown that patriarchy is inherently naturist. (Glazebrook 15)

Ecofeminist philosophy aims to analyse and provide solutions to issues such as “Deforestation, water pollution, farming and food production, and toxins and hazardous waste location must be integrally connected to an understanding of the plight and status of women, people of color, the poor, and children ...” (Glazebrook 15). Ecofeminism tries to streamline mainstream environmental policies to shed light on women and marginalized communities. It exposes the patriarchal hypocrisies and how capitalists frame policies and narratives to muzzle the fragile voices. Yıldız Merve Öztürkin her paper “An Overview of Ecofeminism: Women, Nature and Hierarchies” debates on the passive roles of nature and women in the patriarchal set up:

Since both women and nature are inferior in the male-centred hierarchy, they have passive and dependent roles. Women are passive and dependent because they are seen as incapable beings because of their reproductivity, and it also prevents them from gaining financial freedom. Giving birth is seen as their natural duty; therefore, the society generalises women's dependency on men. On the other hand, since nature is not an active being intrinsically, it cannot overpower humans. That is, humans are intellectually more powerful than animals, and it causes a hierarchy between them and reinforces the dependence of nature. (Merve Öztürk 710).

Women since the inception of mankind were treated unfairly by men. Patriarchy has historically devised different roles for women aligning them with domesticity, caregiving, and emotional labour to keep them engaged as subordinates. Ecofeministic discourse critically deliberates on socio linguistic construct of women by identifying the terminology adapted by the patriarchal framework to demean their physical, psychological, political and economic status. The description of female gender using terms such as “nurturer” “mother” “caretaker” etc. is a linguistic apparatus of male hegemony. These man-made discourses allowed patriarchy to exploit both environment and women. Bronwyn James in her article “Is Ecofeminism Relevant?” states:

Ecofeminists assert that both women and nature have been mutually degraded and devalued.... Central to this assertion lies the assumption that women are closer to nature than men are. Although there is consensus among ecofeminists that women's close association with nature is grounded in their biological function of reproduction... (James 8-9).

Women and nature are colonized by man to extract resources under the garb of legal, cultural and conscious justification to keep them deprived as inferior and subservient to

man. Rosemary Radford Ruether; one of the pioneers in the field of ecofeminism, in her paper “Ecofeminism: First and Third World Women” explains the paradigm of exploitation as:

...the cultural-symbolic patterns by which both women and nature are inferiorized and identified with each other as an ideological superstructure by which the system of economic and legal domination of women, land, and animals is justified and made to appear "natural" and inevitable within a total patriarchal cosmovision. Ecofeminists who stress this socio-economic analysis underlying the patriarchal ideology of subordination of women and nature also wish to include race and class hierarchy as well. (Ruether 35).

Apart from Scio-economic control; the advent of scientific knowledge brought with itself modern discourses and technology that helped patriarchy to further control the narrative against women and nature providing men the authority of exploiting women and plundering natural resources thus enabling them to become master of women and natural resources. Vandana Shiva in her book *Staying Alive Women: Ecology and Survival in India* (1988) describes scientific knowledge as “a patriarchal project”:

At a deeper level, scientific knowledge, on which the development process is based, is itself a source of violence. Modern reductionist science, like development, turns out to be a patriarchal project, which has excluded women as experts, and has simultaneously excluded ecological and holistic ways of knowing which understand and respect nature's processes and interconnectedness as science. (Vandana Shiva 14).

Therefore, we can argue that man with the help of technology and modern scientific knowledge created avenues to subordinate both nature and women and exploited them for maintaining the patriarchal and gender-based bias. The impact was

also felt by the marginalized groups and indigenous communities. Women and nature suffer despite the fact that they provide sustenance to survival of mankind. Ecofeminism considers women more liberal and spiritual than their male counterparts because she bears the compassion and care for biodiversity. The dominating nature of man taught him selfishness and manipulation of resources; therefore, he believes himself the centre of great chain of being and enjoys the impunity to exploit nature and women. Greg Garrard in her book *Ecocriticism* observes that ecofeminism underlines the point that it is not just anthropocentrism which has done great harm to nature but also androcentric dualism which has bestowed superior position to man thus giving them the power and authority to exploit both women and nature:

Deep ecology identifies the anthropocentric dualism humanity/ nature as the ultimate source of anti-ecological beliefs and practices, but ecofeminism also blames the androcentric dualism man/ woman. The first distinguishes humans from nature on the grounds of some alleged quality such as possession of an immortal soul or rationality, and then assumes that this distinction confers superiority upon humans. The second distinguishes men from women on the grounds of some alleged quality such as larger brain size, and then assumes that this distinction confers superiority upon men. (Garrard 26).

Suffering of Tribal Women and Forest Denudation in *The Book of the Hunter*

Indian society has a rich tapestry of social and cultural customs as an effect of tribes, traditions, languages, ethnicity and religions. India, a home of 1.5 billion populations, presents a binary of socio-cultural situations experienced by its inhabitants. Anthropologists and the Constitution of India identify a special class of people denoted by the term tribals or Adivasis residing within the boundaries of the state. The people living in modernised or industrialised urban topographies enjoy the luxurious living

with rest of the world in every walk of life. However, the life of a tribal presents a completely different picture. The reason for categorising the tribals as a different set of people from the rest of the nation can be observed in their manner of living, their habitation, their food habits, their agricultural practices and in their customs. According to tribal co-operative marketing development federation of India limited:

The areas inhabited by the tribal constitute a significant part of the under developed areas of the country. India's population includes nearly one hundred million tribal people. The two main regions of tribal settlement are the country's northeastern states bordering China and Burma, and the highlands and plains of its central and southern regions. The latter is home to more than 80 per cent of the tribes, which differ from the northeastern tribes in ethnicity and in having experienced greater "intrusion of the Indian mainstream and of the pan-Indian model of the state, society, economy and culture". There are also differences in the extent to which the tribes interact with non-tribal communities. While the northeastern tribes are usually isolated communities, the tribes in peninsular India may at times coexist with non-tribal people.

The tribals despite living a life of backwardness and social aloofness are being praised world-wide for being the caretakers of nature and natural resources. Frameworks such as ecocriticism and ecofeminism are being developed across the institutions which take into consideration the role of Adivasis (particularly the women) in preserving and balancing the eco-system and biodiversity.

Mahasweta Devi was an Indian Bengali writer and an environmental activist, who worked tirelessly for the rights and empowerment of the tribal people of West Bengal, Bihar, Madhya Pradesh and Chhattisgarh states of India. She won prestigious awards such as the Sahitya Akademi Award, Jnanpith Award and Ramon Magsaysay Award. The Government of India also

conferred upon her Padma Shri and Padma Vibhushan Awards. These honours stand testimony to her struggle for the forest-people.

The novel *The Book of the Hunter* is a seminal work on tribal and environmental issues. The novel explores the relationship of the tribals with the environment and the apocalyptic decline of tribal customs and their way of life. The text also highlights the erosion of eco-customs and the plight of indigenous women. The story is set in the 16th century medieval Bengal. The book draws inspiration from the epic, poem ‘Abhayamangal’ better known as ‘Chandimangal’ written by great medieval poet Kabikankan Mukundaram Chakrabarti. The novel deals with the ‘Hunter tribe’ known as ‘Shabars’ who lived and survived on forest environs and its resources. Mahasweta Devi explores the slow erosion of Shabars and their tribal way of life as forest land was frequently cleared to make way for settlements. The novel also highlights the struggles and sacrifices of Shabar women.

The novel unfolds the story of Ararha town and the dwelling of Shabar’s “...beyond the town of Ararha, there was the huge jungle called Chandir Bon, at the edge of which lived a tribe of hunters or Akhetiyas” (Devi 41). Novel has a charming setting to present binary tussle of development against the age-old eco-beliefs of Shabar tribe. On the one hand we see the anthropocentrism of the city folks and on the other hand we see the age old eco-customs and biocentrism of the tribal people or the ‘hunters’. Elaborating on this clash of biocentrism vs. anthropocentrism Malcolm L Hunter Jr et al. in their paper, “The Complementary Niches of Anthropocentric and Biocentric Conservationists” observe:

...people who are strongly anthropocentric care only about the welfare of humanity; all other species are resources to be exploited. They would be content in a world dominated by domestic species as long as there was sufficient food, water, and oxygen and whatever other elements of nature

are necessary to provide people with healthy, happy lives. Conversely, people who are strongly biocentric consider *Homo sapiens* no more intrinsically important than any other species. Because of the overwhelming threats people pose to other species, biocentrists would prefer a world with a far lower human population living lifestyles that greatly reduced humanity's impact on wild species, even if it compromised their material well-being. (L. Hunter et al. 642).

Mahasweta Devi through her sensitive portrayal of Shabars brings out the daily struggles of this biocentric tribe as opposed to the anthropocentric people living in Ararha town, who for materialistic desires are hell bent to erode the forests and exploit its resources which has pushed the life of Shabars on the edge of extinction. The society was rapidly changing its core values and the environmental principles were least taken into consideration. The feminine eco-conscious attitude and manner of life remains undeterred despite the hooliganism of patriarchal anthropocentric discourses and actions. The stark contrast between the point of views of male and female psyche is highlighted by the novelist in portrayal of Jagdiswari's contemplation stating, "Shehad never seen any of this before, never seen houses of the type built here, never seen such a high dyke around the drinking-water pond, never seen anything made of red clay like that. Or such white sands below such crystal-clear water." (Devi 41). The character of Jagdiswari is a metanarrative through which the author portrays the triviality of patriarchal discourse. She despite being a Brahmin didn't care for the social norms put forth by the Brahminical patriarchal set up. She easily intermingles with the Adivasi women, and is compassionate for them. She shared food and clothing with them. The eco-conscious ideology of tribals is reflected at another instance when the Shabars cannot bear the sight of developmental sites taking over their environmental habitat, they simply vacate the place and go somewhere else, "When this town Ararha grows larger and the forest is cut down,

you'll see them abandon their settlements and go somewhere else.” (Devi61)

Alongside environmental degradation the novel highlights the plight of Shabar women and their exploitation at the hands of town's people and within tribal society. The symbol of indigenous women's struggles in the novel is Shabar prince Kalya's young wife Phuli who is often referred in the novel by Brahmin priest Mukunda as, “such a shameless girl.” (Devi51). Here the very description of Phuli by the priest Mukunda is indicative of social-subversion achieved by the higher social strata through the language.

The highest jungle deity among Shabar's is Abhayachandi; a female goddess, yet we witness in the novel that women in Shabar tribe are exploited in all possible ways as nature is devastated by men to satisfy their greed. It is the goddess of the jungle who guides and leads Shabars like a mother, “and to everyone and everything! The forest, the animals, the birds, and the Shabars—she gives them all courage and keeps them under her wing.” (Devi 53). Still the women of the tribe hardly possess any rights to execute their wishes, they are supposed to abide men in every domain of life.

Kalya's mother Tejota is the leader of Shabars and is a true symbol of environmental wisdom, “there's nothing that the old woman doesn't know.” (Devi55). She embodies wisdom and compassion like mother earth does for its species ---- rejuvenating, recycling and healing to keep the life possible on earth. She has the wisdom and knowledge to lead her clan like a philosopher. She also acts as doctor as she has knowledge of herbal medicine and treats both animals and humans, “...a nail from the gate of the elephant-shed had got stuck in the sole of its foot. Tejota pulled it out and put medicine bark on it...she's really a wise old woman!” (Devi 55). But the Brahmin priest is so biased that he refuses to acknowledge the traditional ecological wisdom of Tejota, “Mukunda did not believe that a forest-dwelling Shabar could

know much about anything.” (Devi 55). This shows how patriarchy relegates nature and tribal women. Tejota as a woman leader is dedicated to environmental protection and follows eco-guidance in letter and spirit, “The forest itself is our mother.” (Devi 73). The novel rejects the shallow claim of patriarchy that women are not equipped for leadership roles. Through the character of Tejota, Mahasweta Devi establishes that women are gifted with greater consciousness of the environment and prove to be better guides in disseminating environmental wisdom.

The indigenous women were skilled craftswomen possessing problem solving abilities ranging from household chores to doing midwife activities, “There’s no midwife like Gopali. Have no fear. And once the baby is born, drink the herbal concoction Tejota makes and your body will feel all toned again she’ll give the ingredients for the concoction to any pregnant woman who asks” (Devi 84). As the tribals always stayed outside the fold of developed society they have discovered plethora of indigenous medicinal practices to deal with all sorts of day to day ailments and diseases. However, tribal practices were discredited by colonizers not only to set their dispensaries in forest areas to provide medical facilities to their colonial officials but also to extract natural resources from their areas and to make tribals feel backward and ignorant. David Hardiman while explaining about the healing practices among tribals in his paper, “Healing, Medical Power and the Poor: Contests in Tribal India” remarks:

The myths and legends of the tribal people reveal that they suffered from a wide range of ailments - endemic as well as epidemic - in the past. They were left largely to their own devices when ill, with most healing being carried out by relatives and neighbours using herbal and other folk remedies who used herbal remedies, cauterisation, divination and exorcism, treated the more intractable cases. These people were highly respected and had considerable social power. These forms of indigenous healing have continued and evolved, and are still practised very widely

in tribal areas to this day. Today, some of these healers practise a hybrid form of healing that combines ritual with various quasi-allopathic or complementary medical practices. In general, colonial officials, missionaries and the western- educated Indian elites have been un- sympathetic towards such practices, though in recent years drug companies as well as forest officials have sought to exploit their knowledge of herbal remedies. (Hardiman 1405).

The Shabars are hunters, the jungle people they believe in abiding the forest laws, yet Megha; the father of Kalya and husband of Tejota goes against the forest rules by killing a doe, “Megha had killed a doe, and that’s why Danko never bestowed Megha with his knowledge.” (Devi56). This again proves that it is men who transgress natural laws however, the ones who protect environmental sanctity of any community are women yet they are the worst sufferers in the hands of patriarchy.

Sustainable environment is the lifeline for the human survival on the earth. It fulfils all needs of man, “She gives us fruits, flowers, tubers, leaves, wood, honey, resin, medicine herbs, barks, leaves and roots, even animals to hunt. She gives us everything, keeps us alive—doesn’t that make her our mother?” (Devi73). Nature and women are alike they serve man in every possible way to make his life colourful and comfortable. In return, man never acknowledges their role in his life but only exploits them to fulfill his needs and ever-expanding desires. Marlene Dixon in her paper, “On the Super-Exploitation of Women” delineates on pathetic situation of female sex:

The subjugation of the female sex was based on the transformation of their socially necessary labor into a private service for the husband which occurred through the separation of the family from the clan. It was in this context that women's domestic work came to be performed under conditions of virtual slavery. (Dixon2).

The Shabars were not just a scattered community, but a group who had environmental laws to guide their lives and had customs like the people of Ararha town. They also celebrated lot of festivals and performed rituals for different occasions, “it was customary to erect a new birthing hut for the delivery. The new mother took a ritual bath for Shasthi puja on the sixth day after the birth. Then there was a ritual on the twenty-first day and the birthing hut would be demolished.” (Devi 90). However, with the arrival of colonizers tribal customs and rituals were dehumanised forcing them to shift from place to place in search of shelter. This process of dehumanization and forced exile of tribals enabled colonizers to plunder the forest resources. Most of these tribal rituals were performed by tribal women and hence women were doubly marginalized with the advent of colonization.

The methods and cultural knowledge applied by indigenous women at the time of child birth were more effective than the process prevalent in upper caste society, “Mukunda’s wife said faintly, when Shibu and Shiuli were born, I had pains that rose and fell, they almost killed me...and this time...” (Devi 91). But all the tribal methods and cultural practices were discarded and jeopardised with time by colonizers and upper castes. Tribal practices were dehumanised and, in this way, tribals were put to subjugation and forced to move from place to place. The midwife used to suggest fruits and vegetables to the mother for her good health after childbirth and used to perform all kinds of rituals to save the child and the mother from any kind of harm. They used to take care of the mother till she recuperates, “My daughter-in-law can stay with you until you get your strength back” (Devi 92). This explains that indigenous people had a method and practices for everything. The pivotal work was done by indigenous women to maintain their culture and customs but with time they were robbed of such customs and forced to be without work and their whole lifestyle was disturbed. Similarly, the forest resources that helped our ecology to sustain our lives were robbed and plundered unsustainably by man to fill its materialistic greed.

Dehumanization and coercion of women by their counter parts is one of the major debates in Mahasweta Devi's novel under discussion. Phuli's husband's cruelty towards her is explicitly visible when she recounts the trauma that she undergoes at the hands of her husband, prince Kalya; "But he wouldn't listen to me. He'll just beat me, asking, why didn't you bring home rice? Why didn't you cook a pot of it? My, how his punches hurt!" (Devi 75). The correlation of feminine abuse and environmental exploitation by men can be observed at another instance when Kalya demeans his wife with phallogocentric remarks; "didn't your father carry off five deer skins and a wild boar for himself." (Devi 51). This is how patriarchy controls both nature and women by declaring itself their master and by exploiting them at will. Kalya got gifts and appreciation from elders for killing animals, "Kalya is a great warrior and hero, you know. He wasn't yet fifteen years old when he killed his first tiger. He brought it to show to the king and he got clothes and two gamchhas as a reward." (Devi 59). This shows how men exude power and control over nature and women through male centric narratives of violence, exploitation and dominance.

He used to beat her on silly things to show dominance over her, "I know. Kalya has beaten you...just like that. He said, 'you roasted rabbit, why didn't you roast some *bengchishak* with it?'" (Devi 96). The book is full of instances where we see Kalya dominating Phuli inside home and outside in the jungle he kills wild animals to satisfy his manly ego of being a brave hunter, "if you went out hunting, you'd come back with tiger. You'd say, 'why should you sell all the skins? I want to sleep on a tiger skin, with my head on the tiger's head.'" (Devi 99). Since childhood Kalya had a great fascination for animal domination which symbolizes the male desire of controlling environment. The novel narrates how Kalya, "dragged six-year-old Phuli over by the hair, saying, 'This is going to be my wife, you hear that ma.'" (Devi99). Kalya used to dominate Phuli since childhood like she was an object of entertainment for him, "... Kalya had grabbed her by the hair and dragged her home, screaming, aren't you, my bride? How can you play with those boys?" (Devi 128). The novelist by such

nuanced incidents has highlighted the powerlessness of female gender and how patriarchy treats them as objects to satisfy men. Phuli had to bear dual trauma of marital violence as well the management of domestic responsibility.

The climax scene in which Phuli dies is the metaphorical and symbolic representation of indigenous and marginalized woman's death in the hands of patriarchy. She is forced to commit suicide due to male-dominated narratives. Her role in society is squeezed and she is just objectified to decorate the male world, and at the end we see her so weak that she couldn't survive without male support because she was never made independent but was always given patriarchal crutches to survive:

Phuli's naked body was floating on the water, her hand and feet were tied up in the two edges of the sari, and a corner of the cloth was clenched in her teeth. Who knows exactly how, but Phuli had managed to tie up her own hands, pulling and tugging with a sari held in her teeth. (Devi 147).

Mahasweta devi's novel *The Book of the Hunter* explores the themes of environmental degradation, gender marginalization and tribal resistance. The novel critiques the colonial and caste-based prejudices prevalent in our society. The narrative highlights the impact of anthropocentric and androcentric worldviews on ecology and women and calls out capitalist and feudal forces for the disruption of relationship between environment and man.

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